

Comparative Analysis of Transformer-Based and CNN Models for High-Throughput Wheat Head Detection

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Abstract:

Wheat head or spike detection is significant for phenotyping because it can be directly correlated to yield and is an indicator of yield potential. Historically, wheat head counting was a labor-intensive and error prone process. Use of Deep Learning (DL) techniques has automated this process allowing automated wheat head detection and counting using high resolution imagery, allowing large-scale, High Throughput Phenotyping (HTP). Despite the use of advanced technologies, wheat head detection is a challenging task due to high environmental variability, cultivar differences, and head overlap. Several attempts have been made to make the DL models more robust and the wheat head datasets more diverse to improve the

detection accuracy and reliability. With the introduction of advanced DL architectures, there has been continuous improvement in accuracy of head detection. In this study, we have evaluated the performance of three different cutting-edge DL models - YOLOv10x, RetinaNet, and MM-Grounding DINO for wheat head detection. We have also combined two different wheat datasets, Global Wheat Head Detection (GWHD) 2021 and SPIKE dataset to get a diverse dataset with a wide range of genotypes. This study aims to contribute to the ongoing evolution of wheat head detection techniques and provide an insight into how these three models perform for this task.

Keywords: *Wheat head detection, High-throughput phenotyping, Deep learning, Convolutional neural networks, Transformer models.*

Introduction

Wheat is one of the major crops in the world, serving as a staple food source for most of the

world's population and playing a significant role in ensuring global food security (Shiferaw et al., 2013). In the face of climate change and population growth, it is crucial to increase global

wheat production by developing genotypes with high yield potential. This can be achieved by expedited breeding efforts leveraging HTP techniques to efficiently analyze and select desirable traits at scale. With the rapid and large-scale data collection and analysis in HTP, it has now been possible to collect data on various yield-related traits, select desirable traits, and accelerate breeding programs (Xiao et al., 2022). In wheat, head or spike count and other spike traits are direct indicators of yield, and these traits, along with other phenotypic traits, help breeders in selecting promising cultivars (Zhou et al., 2021; Würschum et al., 2018; Gaju et al., 2009).

Automated detection of wheat heads helps breeders to monitor yield-related traits without relying on time- and resource-intensive manual counting of wheat heads (Hasan et al., 2018). Moreover, advanced imaging techniques and DL facilitate automated wheat head detection with high levels of accuracy and reliability. DL models are capable of processing high-resolution imagery of agricultural fields and perform better if large volumes of data are available, enabling HTP (Madec et al., 2019). In addition, the use of high-resolution imagery allows DL models to capture fine-grained details of plants in the images, enabling precise phenotypic measurements. DL models, when trained on diverse datasets covering different environments, can be robust across environmental variability.

Machine Learning (ML) and DL have driven significant strides in automated detection technologies in a wide range of domains ranging from agriculture, such as in weed and crop monitoring (Shrestha et al., 2024) to autonomous systems such as advanced driver assistant systems (Ojha et al., 2022). In addition to CNN based DL models, transformer-based architectures, including large language models (LLMs) and computer vision models, are being widely adopted across multiple domains (Chataut et al., 2024; Aryal et al., 2024). For instance, transformer-based architectures performed well in the segmentation of microbes on metallic objects (Gurung et al., 2023). However, using DL methods for wheat head

detection is challenging because of the variability in field conditions, lighting, plant orientation, and soil background in the imagery or dataset. In addition, as wheat is grown with minimal row spacing and there are multiple overlapping heads on the same plant, DL models struggle to perform well, leading to false negatives or false positives. The genotypic and phenotyping diversity of wheat also pose challenges to the improvement of DL models' performance for wheat head detection. Hence, the diversity of training data is equally important as the DL model complexity for the accurate detection of wheat heads (Fourati et al., 2021).

As more labeled datasets from a wide range of environmental conditions and genotypes become available, continuous improvement in the detection accuracy and robustness of DL models can be achieved. Several attempts have been made by researchers across the world to improve the accuracy of wheat head detection by adopting state-of-the-art detection models and creating diverse datasets (David et al., 2021; Fourati et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2022; Wen et al., 2022). In our study, we evaluate the performance of three cutting-edge DL models – YOLOv11, RetinaNet, and MM-Grounding DINO – for wheat head detection. By combining the Global Wheat Head Detection (GWHD) 2021 dataset (David et al., 2021) and the SPIKE dataset, we have created a diverse dataset representing a wide range of genotypes and environmental conditions. The aim of this study is to analyze the effectiveness of these state-of-the-art DL models for wheat head detection in varied conditions and contribute to the ongoing evolution of automated wheat head detection for HTP.

Materials and Methods

System Overview

The initial step in the workflow for comparative analysis of wheat head detection is the collection and compilation of dataset for the models. GWHD_2021 and SPIKE dataset were used and preprocessed to ensure compatibility before moving into the model training step.

Figure 1. Workflow for the Comparative Analysis of Wheat Head Detection Models

The models are then evaluated using several performance metrics to allow for the comparison of the models.

Dataset Description

In this study, we utilized two datasets: the GWHD_2021 dataset (David et al., 2021) and the SPIKE dataset (Hasan et al., 2018). These datasets cover a wide range of developmental stages of wheat and offer more data diversity. Notably, the GWHD_2021 dataset and the SPIKE dataset differ in several key aspects, including camera angles, illumination conditions, and other environmental factors. The GWHD_2021 dataset consists of images captured from different camera angles compared to those in the SPIKE dataset. Additionally, variations in illumination and other factors between the two datasets contribute to a broader range of visual conditions. This diversity in the final dataset aids to enhance the robustness and generalizability of the detection models, enhancing their performance by training them to handle various real-world scenarios encountered by researchers and agronomists across the world.

The Global Wheat Head Detection Dataset is the largest dataset for detection of wheat heads in optical images. Initially it was created in 2020 consisting of 4700 high-resolution RGB images and 190000 labelled wheat heads collected from several countries around the world. The GWHD_2021 dataset was created to provide a

better benchmark for the community by refining the GWHD_2020 dataset. It involved removing poor-quality images, re-labeling for consistency, and including a wider range of developmental stages from the original sites. In GWHD_2021, 1200 new images were added from 5 additional countries resulting in 120,000 new labeled wheat heads. Hence, GWHD_2021 consists of 6500 1024x1024 images containing 275,187 unique wheat heads with corresponding bounding boxes. GWHD_2021 dataset consists of 3600 train images, 1400 test images and 1400 validation images.

Table 1. Dataset Description

Category	Number of images	Head Count
Training Data	5254	252867
Validation Data	1476	44347
Total	6730	297214

The SPIKE dataset includes over 300 images representing ten different wheat varieties at three distinct growth stages, providing a comprehensive view of wheat spike development. Each image is meticulously annotated with bounding boxes that highlight the locations of wheat spikes, facilitating the training of deep learning models for accurate spike detection.

Figure 2. Diversity of Images in the Dataset Used for Training and Validating the DL Models

Dataset Collection and Compilation

Most of our training data was sourced from the GWHD_2021 dataset, utilizing both its training and test images. To further enrich our training set, we incorporated additional images from the SPIKE dataset, specifically selecting positive examples that feature clear wheat head annotations. This strategic combination was aimed at enhancing the diversity and robustness of the training data, allowing our model to generalize better across different conditions and variations in wheat head appearances. For validation, we employed the validation set from the GWHD_2021 dataset.

We merged 1,400 training images and 1,400 testing images from the GWHD_2021 dataset with 315 positive examples from the SPIKE dataset to create our training dataset. This approach was intended to maximize the diversity of wheat head representations within the training set, enhancing the model's ability to accurately detect wheat heads across a wide range of scenarios. By combining these datasets, the training phase provided the model with a richer and more varied set of images, contributing to improved detection performance. For

validation, we utilized 1,400 validation images from the GWHD_2021 dataset.

Dataset Preprocessing

The original annotations in GWHD_2021 dataset was provided in COCO format, which is widely used for object detection tasks. Similarly, the annotations of the SPIKE dataset were in Separate Bounding Box and Class Label Annotations format with one TSV file for bounding box coordinates and another TSV file for corresponding class labels for each image. However, our chosen models, YOLOv10 requires annotations in YOLO format, MM-Grounding DINO requires annotations in COCO format and RetinaNet requires annotations in either COCO format or in a CSV file containing annotations for all images where each row represents one bounding box. To prepare the datasets for training and evaluation, we converted the annotations of both the GWHD_2021 and the SPIKE datasets to align with these requirements. This conversion involved reformatting the annotations to match the input formats expected by each model, facilitating smooth integration and training processes. The modifications included adjusting

the structure and content of annotation files to align with the format specifications for bounding boxes and class labels required by YOLOv10, RetinaNet, and MM-Grounding DINO. This step was crucial for accurate training and evaluation of the models on the provided datasets.

- **YOLOv10 Format:** For each image in the dataset, a corresponding text file is created. Each line in this file represents a bounding box, specifying the class ID, the normalized center coordinates (`center_x`, `center_y`), and the normalized width and height of the box relative to the image dimensions. This format is optimized for YOLO models, which require a simple and lightweight text-based format to facilitate fast detection.
- **RetinaNet Format:** Annotations are stored in a CSV file, with each row representing a single bounding box for a specific image. The row includes the filename, bounding box coordinates (`xmin`, `ymin`, `xmax`, `ymax`), and a class label. In this case, the class label is set to "wheat" for all entries. This format is well-suited for RetinaNet, which requires structured data in a tabular format for bounding box localization and classification.
- **MM-Grounding DINO Format (COCO Format):** A JSON file is generated following the COCO dataset structure, which includes image metadata, bounding box coordinates, and category labels. This comprehensive format provides detailed annotation information and is compatible with models like Grounding DINO, which use the COCO format to handle complex object detection tasks with multiple categories and metadata.

Overview of Detection Models

YOLOv10 introduces advanced architectural improvements and optimization techniques to enhance both speed and accuracy compared to its predecessor in the YOLO (You Only Look Once) family. Notably, YOLOv10 employs a novel Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS)-free training approach using consistent dual assignments, eliminating the need for non-

maximum suppression during inference. This is achieved by combining one-to-many and one-to-one label assignment strategies, allowing the model to receive rich supervision during training while maintaining high efficiency during inference. Additionally, YOLOv10 incorporates a holistic efficiency-accuracy driven model design strategy that optimizes various components of the architecture.

RetinaNet is a single-stage object detection model designed to provide a balance between high accuracy and fast inference times. Unlike two-stage detectors like Faster R-CNN, which first generate candidate object proposals and then classify them, RetinaNet performs object classification and bounding box regression in a single forward pass. Its primary contribution is the introduction of Focal Loss, which addresses the problem of class imbalance commonly encountered in object detection tasks. By reducing the loss contribution from well-classified examples, Focal Loss enables the model to focus more on difficult, misclassified instances. This allows RetinaNet to maintain strong performance, particularly when detecting small objects or classes that are less frequently represented, without a major reduction in speed. The architecture of RetinaNet relies on a Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) backbone, which enables the model to handle objects at different scales by using feature maps at multiple resolutions.

MM-Grounding-DINO is a cutting-edge, open-source improvement of the Grounding-DINO model, designed to address key tasks in multi-modal vision, including Open-Vocabulary Detection (OVD), Phrase Grounding (PG), and Referring Expression Comprehension (REC). Built using the MMDetection toolbox, it facilitates seamless integration and scalability across multiple datasets and detection applications. MM-Grounding-DINO employs a multi-modal architecture that processes both visual and textual features simultaneously, allowing it to effectively detect objects within images based on a given textual description. While the model retains the core structure of Grounding-DINO, it introduces several enhancements, most notably the incorporation

of new datasets such as COCO, Objects365, GRIT, and V3Det for pretraining. These diverse datasets enhance the model's ability to generalize and perform well in open-set environments, improving its effectiveness in downstream tasks like grounding and detection.

Experimentation

The YOLOv10, RetinaNet, and MM-Grounding DINO models were trained using a unified training dataset. This dataset included images from both the training and testing splits of the GWHD_2021 dataset, complemented by positive examples from the SPIKE dataset. This combination ensured a diverse and representative set of images for effective model training. Our experiments were conducted utilizing the freely available NVIDIA P100 GPU on the Kaggle, which provided a convenient and accessible way for training our models. We employed pytorch as a primary deep learning framework for implementing models. We aim to find out which model performs the best among the three in the field of wheat head detection.

YOLOv10 Training and Hyperparameters

The YOLOv10x model was trained for a total of 45 epochs with a batch size of 8. Input images were standardized to 800×800 pixels to ensure consistent dimensions across the dataset. The training process employed an automatic optimizer with an initial learning rate of 0.01, which was adjusted according to a predefined learning rate schedule. A 3-epoch warmup phase was included, starting with an initial learning rate of 0.1 and a warmup momentum of 0.8. Additional training parameters included a momentum value of 0.937 and a weight decay of 0.0005. To enhance computational efficiency, Automatic Mixed Precision (AMP) was enabled. Data augmentation techniques such as horizontal flipping (with a probability of 0.5), random scaling, and mosaic augmentation were applied during the initial 10 epochs, with auto-augmentation configured to use randaugment to further improve data diversity.

The training process incorporated overlap mask regularization with a mask ratio of 4, while dropout was not used. This comprehensive setup ensured both effective training and

evaluation of the YOLOv10 model, balancing performance with efficient use of computational resources.

RetinaNet Training and Hyperparameters

We employed a ResNet-152 backbone within the RetinaNet model. The training process began by initializing the backbone with pre-trained weights from a ResNet-101 checkpoint, which had been trained on ImageNet. This allowed us to leverage the strong feature extraction capabilities of ResNet, particularly for identifying intricate features in the wheat heads. The ResNet backbone was fine-tuned to adapt to our wheat detection task, while the classification and regression heads of the RetinaNet model were trained from scratch. This hybrid approach was necessary to transfer generalized features learned from ImageNet while modifying the model for the detection of wheat heads.

To improve the model's generalization ability, we applied various data augmentations, including normalization, resizing, and horizontal flipping. These augmentations were critical in simulating real-world variations in wheat head appearances. We set a confidence threshold of 0.3 to filter out low-confidence detections and used an Intersection-over-Union (IoU) threshold of 0.5 to determine true positives based on the overlap between predicted and ground truth bounding boxes. To ensure efficiency, we capped the maximum number of detections per image at 100.

For optimization, the Adam optimizer was employed with a learning rate of $1e-5$, and a learning rate scheduler was used to reduce the learning rate when validation loss plateaued. We trained the model for 100 epochs, incorporating gradient clipping with a threshold of 5 to prevent overfitting and manage exploding gradients. The total loss function minimized was a combination of classification loss (focal loss) and regression loss (smooth L1) for bounding box predictions.

MM-Grounding DINO Training and Hyperparameters

We utilized the MM-Grounding DINO framework with the grounding_dino_swin-

t_pretrain_obj365 model for wheat head detection. The dataset used in training this model comprises images, with annotations following the COCO format. To facilitate detection of wheat heads, we defined a single class labeled as "wheat". The training dataset was augmented using a combination of random flips and random choice resize operations across a range of scales, with additional cropping to account for the high aspect ratio of the images. For data loading, we employed a custom pipeline that processed images and annotations in batches, utilizing a sampler to ensure a balanced distribution of image aspect ratios.

The model was optimized using the AdamW optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0001 and weight decay of 0.0001. A gradient clipping strategy with a maximum norm of 0.1 was applied to stabilize training. Training was conducted over 8 epochs. We initialized our model from pre-trained weights provided by the MMDetection team.

Validation Metrics

In this study, we utilized three key validation metrics— Average Precision (AP), precision, and recall—to evaluate the performance of YOLOv10, RetinaNet, and MM-Grounding DINO models for wheathead detection. Intersection over Union (IoU) measures the overlap between the predicted bounding box and the ground truth box, which is essential for determining whether a detection is considered a true positive. IoU is calculated as:

$$IoU = \frac{\text{Area of Overlap}}{\text{Area of Union}} \quad (1)$$

where the Area of Overlap is the intersection area between the predicted and ground truth boxes, and the Area of Union is their combined area. A detection is considered a true positive if the IoU exceeds a predefined threshold, i.e. 0.5 in our case.

Precision represents the ratio of True Positive (TP) detections to the total number of positive detections and is critical for assessing how accurately each model identified wheat heads

without generating False Positives (FP). Mathematically, precision is defined as:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{\max(TP + FP, \epsilon)} \quad (2)$$

where TP represents the number of correctly identified wheat heads, and FP refers to instances where the model incorrectly predicted the presence of wheat heads. The small constant ϵ is introduced to prevent division by zero in the case where there are no positive predictions. Precision was particularly important for reducing false positives, which could lead to over-estimations in crop yield or incorrect decisions in downstream agricultural processes.

Recall, the ratio of true positive detections to the total number of actual instances, provided insights into the models' sensitivity and their capacity to detect most wheat heads, even in challenging conditions. High recall ensured that the models captured most relevant wheat heads, but it needed to be balanced with precision to avoid an excessive number of false positives. Mathematically, recall is defined as:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3)$$

We also used Average Precision (AP) as a metric for evaluating model performance, as it provides a comprehensive measure of performance by considering both precision and recall across various thresholds. AP is computed by integrating the precision-recall curve, which plots precision versus recall at different threshold levels. It can also be defined as the area under the precision-recall curve.

In this paper, Average Precision (AP) is used as the primary metric for evaluating performance. Since the analysis is focused on a single class, the mean Average Precision (mAP) and AP are equivalent in this context.

Results

The evaluation results for the wheat head detection task are summarized in table below, presenting the performance of three models YOLOv10, RetinaNet, and MM-Grounding-DINO.

Table 2. Performance Comparison of Models Used for Wheat Head Detection

Model	AP@50	Precision	Recall
RetinaNet	0.841	0.839	0.860
YOLOv10	0.912	0.894	0.844
MM-Grounding-DINO	0.922	0.888	0.924

Among the models, MM-Grounding-DINO achieved the highest AP@50 of 0.922, demonstrating its effectiveness in detecting wheat heads with both high precision and recall. With a precision of 0.888 and recall of 0.924, MM-Grounding-DINO performed well in detecting the highest number of true positives

while maintaining a relatively low number of false positives. This model proved to be the most robust for this task, striking a strong balance between precision and recall.

YOLOv10 also delivered competitive performance with an AP@50 of 0.912, achieving the highest precision of 0.894, indicating its strength in minimizing false positives. However, YOLOv10's recall of 0.844 was slightly lower compared to the other two models, suggesting that it missed more wheat heads. RetinaNet, on the other hand, demonstrated the lowest AP@50 of 0.841. With a precision of 0.839 and recall of 0.860, RetinaNet's performance was more balanced but less accurate than the other models in terms of overall detection.

In summary, MM-Grounding-DINO exhibited the best overall performance, particularly in maintaining both high precision and recall, making it the most effective model for wheat head detection. YOLOv10 showed a clear strength in precision, while RetinaNet, although balanced, fell behind the other models in detection accuracy.

Figure 3. Wheat Head Detection Results:
(a) MM-Grounding DINO (b) YOLOv10, and (c) RetinaNet

Similarly, the figure above offers a qualitative comparison of the wheat head detection results from the three models. The bounding box predictions highlight how each model handles various environmental conditions and wheat head appearances. The predictions from MM-Grounding DINO are tight and accurate, demonstrating its robustness in localizing wheat heads even in dense or cluttered scenes. Similarly, YOLOv10 also performed well but had the tendency to miss a few smaller or occluded wheat heads, as indicated by its slightly lower recall. The predictions from RetinaNet, where the bounding boxes are less precise, particularly for smaller or overlapping wheat heads.

These visualizations provide insights into each model's capability to detect wheat heads in real-world scenarios, complementing the quantitative evaluation in Table 2.

Discussion

In this study, the MM-Grounding DINO outperformed YOLOv10 and RetinaNet due to its ability to detect wheat heads in challenging conditions that include overlapping wheat heads and complex backgrounds. Hence, our analysis revealed that the transformer-based models can be more efficient in detection of wheat heads in comparison to the CNN models, especially under challenging conditions. The performance of the transformer-based models can be attributed to their architecture that are effective in capturing long-range dependencies and contextual information, making them robust in situations where the traditional CNN models may struggle.

However, using different methods that include model regularization, model ensemble, and data augmentation can improve the precision of CNN based models (Hasan et al., 2018; Fourati et al., 2021). Using these techniques can improve the generalization ability and robustness of CNN-based models. Future research could be in the domain of exploring the potential of using

the strengths of both types of models to further improve the wheat head detection accuracy.

Conclusion

This study revealed that the performance of transformer-based models, specifically MM-Grounding DINO, is better compared to the CNN-based models like YOLOv10 and RetinaNet in detecting wheat heads under challenging conditions, that include overlapping heads and complex backgrounds. The relatively better performance of MM-Grounding DINO can be due to its ability to capture complex spatial and contextual relationships, proving it to be more effective in field environments with high variability. Even though CNN models face limitations in such conditions, using techniques such as regularization, model ensembles, and data augmentation can improve their detection ability and overall robustness. Future research may explore the use of advanced model training and validation techniques such as regularization, data augmentations, ensemble methods, and early stopping to ensure better and more meaningful comparisons between the models.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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